

APPENDIX – Evaluation of the C2M Model

This report presents an evaluation of the C2M communication maturity model. Section 1 introduces the planning of the survey and the evaluation made by experts on the characteristics and elements of the proposed model and its applicability in real projects.

1 SURVEY BASED ON EXPERT OPINION

According to Hakim (1987), small samples can be used to develop, test and explain a certain proposition, especially in the first phases of the research. In this sense, Beechan *et. al.* (2005) affirm that the studies use small samples to obtain feedback of specialists to evaluate the development of models that support a knowledge area. For example, Dyba (2000) used 11 specialists to conduct a review process about the critical success factors in a process of software improvement, with basis in data collected from 120 organizations. El Eman and Madhavji (1996) interviewed 30 specialists to conceive a tool to evaluate the success in the requirement engineering.

The value of the opinion of the specialist or its knowledge also is recognized in an evaluation of the software quality that suggests methods to capture formally the opinion of the specialist (Rosqvist *et. al.*, 2003). So, is possible to say that the software engineering community has given more importance and credibility (reliability) to the studies that use the technique of specialized opinion.

Corroborating with this affirmation, other researches had evidenced the relevance of this technique, like for example, Kitchenham *et. al.* (2002) executed an analysis of precision of several methods of effort estimative using the opinion of specialists. This research revealed that through statistical analysis, a process of human estimative centered in the opinion of specialists can overcome substantially simple models of function point analysis. At last, the work of Beecham *et. al.* (2005) that through its research with specialists evaluated a maturity model to software requirement engineering aligned to the CMMI model.

For this reason, researchers and professionals that work in the area of software engineering tend to adopt the technique of opinion of specialists to evaluate their proposal, aiming to obtain a valuable feedback and an effective evaluation.

1.1 OPINION OF EXPERTS

The opinion of experts in certain matter can be defined as a series of scientific efforts used to interpret the data, foresee the behavior of a system, and evaluate uncertainties (Cooke, 1991). It refers to speculations, suppositions and estimates of people whose are considered specialists in a knowledge area to the extent that they serve as a process of knowledge acquisition in any decision process (Cooke, 1991, Li and Smidts, 2003).

The increasing search for the opinion of specialists, especially in academic researches, is justified by the fact that many knowledge areas and their processes of decision taking are still immature or under construction (Li and Smidts, 2003).

Our process for to gather the opinion of experts was inspired in the work of Li and Smidts (2003), and it is composed of the following steps:

- **Problem Statement.** The background and problem need to be clearly systematized and defined;
- **Selection of Experts.** A number of experts must to be identified based on a set of criteria which should include the credibility, knowledge, ability, and dependability of experts;
- **Elicitation of Opinion.** This step poses the right question and ensures conditions of conduction to an elicitation process;
- **Aggregation of Opinion.** The idea is to reach an aggregated opinion or a consensus based on which a decision can be made;
- **DecisionMaking.** This last step makes the decision based on aggregated opinion

It is worth to highlight that the software engineering has used in its researches the opinion of specialists. However, there are some controversies (Kitchenham et. al., 2007) and skepticism in the scientific community about this matter, and until the present moment, there is no consensus. Kitchenham et. al. (2007) affirms that the main problem is the dependence of informal proofs that might be

influenced by the opinion of the experts. That is, depending on the specialist, its bias (cultural, origin or self-confidence) can distort the information he pass.

Finally, according to Li and Smidts (2003), the number of specialists needed in a study, the identification of the bias, and the technique adopted to the aggregation of the opinion of the experts are questions which must be planned and clarified in the beginning of the study. This way, the adoption of the evaluation of the research based in the opinion of specialists will be more effective. In the next sections, these questions will be described in details.

1.2 THE NUMBER OF EXPERTS

Garcia (2010) says that if a specialist is perfect (that is, he have infinite knowledge about the theme and never make mistakes), only one specialist is needed to the elicitation process. However, there is a tendency to follow up with as many specialists as possible, justified by a perception of security in the numbers (quantity of specialists). In this sense, Li and Smidts (2003) say that the objective of the opinion of experts is “the acquisition of knowledge of the real world”, the capture of the specialist’s experience (challenges, lessons learned, etc.).

To this thesis, 110 potential candidates were selected, composing the group of specialists for this research. They represent a group of specialists with capacity to evaluate and contribute to the improvement of the C2M model. Despite the reduced sample, 110 specialists is considered an adequate number. As notorious in the literature, the inquired sample is satisfactory to the current study, once it is qualified by renowned specialists, with large experience in DSD and software quality process. In practice, from the selected sample, only 55 specialists participated of this study. The next session will describe the process of their selection.

1.3 EXPERT SELECTION IN THIS STUDY

In an ideal scenario, the specialists must be carefully chosen, taking in account some factors, like his knowledge in the research area according to NUREG-1150 (1989 apud GARCIA, 2010, p. 78). However, there is not a well-defined and known standard (Li and Smidts, 2003), for this selection or choice of specialists. In light of the above, is relevant to formulate a set of criteria which must be used to systematize the process of selection. NUREG-1150 (1989 apud Garcia, 2010, p 78) presents a set of guidelines to this selection:

- The specialists must have experience proved by publications or services of consulting or management in the areas related to the theme of the study;
- Every specialist must be sufficiently versatile to be able to deal with very questions concerning to the studied theme, and a wide experience to know how they will be put in practice;
- The specialists must represent a great variety/diversity of experiences (e.g.: academic knowledge, consulting, laboratories, etc.);
- The specialists must be willing to participate of the research and available to pass the requested information according to the method of data gathering to be used.

It should be pointed that the specialists also are subject to some biases, particularly when forced to opine about subjects outside their knowledge domain (SLOVIC, 1987). For this reason, the specialists should be consulted only about events relative to their area of specialty; the experience and information relevant which contributed to their evaluation should be additionally required since, even the specialists have a wide knowledge, they might have difficulties to attribute probabilities (SKJONG; WENTWORTH, 2001).

We selected 110 specialists based in the previous guidelines, but only 55 participated on the research. The main requirements to participate on the study were: i) have a minimum of three years of experience (theoretical or practical) in DSD; ii) have knowledge in improvement of the software process, especially in quality models, like: CMMI, MPS and ISO. Therefore, according to the recommendations of the NUREG-1150 (. 1989 apud Garcia, 2010, p 78), were selected specialists of the industry and academy, from different companies and universities, as well as from different places.

1.4 EXPERT BIASES IN THIS STUDY

Tversky and Kahneman (1974) divided the experts in two classes: those with biases originated from the local they live or work and those with biases from the excess of confidence. An additional method to decrease the biases from the excess of confidence is to encourage the specialists to find reasons that contradict their initial opinions. However, the biases from the local or work may be corrected by the method of Bayesian aggregation (Chhibber et al, 1992), (Li and Smidts, 2003).

In this thesis, we defined the process for the elicitation of opinion of specialists, such that the specialists provided clear and detailed explanations about the evaluation of the C2M model. Therefore, they also were contacted to clarifications about the evaluation. So, we had no evidence of bias or prejudices about the participation in the research.

1.5 EXPERTS OPINION AGGREGATION IN THIS STUDY

Li and Smidts (2003) say that when the aggregation methods had been used, they vary from easy-to-use methods, like the simple calculation of the arithmetic average of the specialists, to more complex techniques (Chidamber e Kemerer, 1994) and the Bayesian aggregation (Chhibber et al., 1992). Still about the aggregation of the opinion of the experts, Keeney (1992) defined a process called Value-Focused Thinking (VFT) on which is searched the identification of the values and knowledge that the researcher will use as a guide to the process. The VFT approach is a way to identify desirable decision situations and so collect the benefits of these situations to solve them.

In this doctorate research, we adopted the aggregation method based in the arithmetic average, based in the answers (analysis of the data) of the specialists. It is important to highlight that no bias was perceived during the investigation. Furthermore, all the specialists were equally weighted during the aggregation, once there was not observed a significant difference in terms of their credibility and importance.

2 RESEARCH APPROACH

The approach to this study was based in the recommendations from Li and Smidts (2003) and motivated by the work of Garcia (2010). It is organized in four phases. In the first phase, the objective was: define, evaluate and validate the script of the guided interview. In the second phase, the specialists were selected and contracted according to the guidelines discussed in the Section 6.1.3. In the third phase, the invitation to participate on the interview was sent to the specialists and after the acceptance the data was collected. Finally, in the fourth phase, the data were analyzed aiming to characterize the C2M model in what concerns to it viability, based in the opinion of experts. The next sections discuss every phase in details.

2.1 THE SURVEY

The research was composed by an interview script developed after a wide literature review, with strong influence of works related to the DSD area (Prikladnicki et. al., 2004), (Prikladnicki et. al., 2009, Santos et. al., 2012), (Da Silva et. al., 2011)) and Opinion studies ((**Beecham et. al., 2005**), (Farias Junior et. al., 2012), (Li and Smidts, 2003)) among others. Furthermore, we counted with the experience of our research group (GP2 group, of the Federal University of Pernambuco – UFPE).

The first version of the research was defined in the beginning of 2014 and was reviewed for two months. The review was performed together with three researchers (one with theoretical and practical experience in software quality improvement, and the other two experienced in the DSD area). It is important to point that these researchers do not participated of the research, but made part of the pilot project that was performed to estimate the time necessary to the respondent conclude the investigation/interview, and raise other relevant aspects.

During this review process, four versions of the research were generated. The main improvement in relation to the first version was related to the order of the questions, the decrease of the script size, as well as adjusts in some clarifying points in the questions.

2.2 THE QUESTIONS

The main aim of our study was to evaluate the viability of the C2M model, as well as its adaptation based in the opinion of specialists. In this sense, the questions were elaborated in relation to: role of the specialist (academy or industry), the way that the maturity factors are distributed in the levels of the model; the specification, description of the main objective of every maturity level; objectives related to the maturity factors; descriptions and objectives of every practice in the model and, if is possible to an organization to perceive and obtain in the incipient levels the benefits of the effective communication, outside the highest maturity levels proposed by the C2M.

The final script was composed by 38 questions with open and closed questions and was projected to be concluded in approximately one hour. Our previous experience in similar studies and the orientations published in the literature ((Gil,

1999), (Yin, 2009), (Andrade, 2007), (Gressler, 2004) and (Li and Smidts, 2003)) were very important to its conception.

2.3 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

Before the interview, the script was sent by email to all the specialists in July, 2014, and next the interviews were appointed (some face-to-face, others through Skype). In August, 2014 all the interviews were finished and collected to analysis. In some cases, we needed to contact the respondent to mitigate doubt or clarify some answers that could lead to diverse interpretations. In the study, ten specialists were contacted to clarify some questions, mainly related to the objectives and practices of the C2M model. It is worth to point that the interview script applied in this research was submitted to the Cronbach's alpha test through the SPSS software and as result was indicated an acceptable reliability to the scale of 0,70.

2.4 CHARACTERIZATION OF THE EXPERTS

Most of the fifty-five specialists that participated of the study are resident in Brazil, with predominance on the state of Pernambuco (Figure 1). Two participants were out of the country (USA and Germany). Still about the characterization of the participants, fourteen work exclusively in the industry, nineteen work exclusively in the academy, while twenty-two work in both (Figure 2). From the participants of the research, fifty-two have the basic formation in computing, one in administration and the other two in communication. Furthermore, there are graduated, forty have the master degree, seven are doctors and one is a post doctor in computer science. The other four are post graduated in "Lato Senso" courses in computer science. All the participants had acted actively in the last years in the DSD area.

Figure 1 – Location of the respondents. the author

Figure 2 - Type of expertise. Source: the author

3 RESULTS OF THE SURVEY

This section presents the analysis of the data collected in the research, discussing in details the main questions and pointing some correlation points that must be took in consideration.

3.1 C2M STRUCTURE

In this question, we asked if the quantity and the organization of the levels in the C2M model are proper to evaluate the maturity of the communication. The

objective was to identify if the distribution of the levels and evolutionary paths are well-defined and understandable (Figure 3).

Figure 3 - C2M organization is suitable for evaluating communication maturity. Source: the author

We that there are convergent positions about the potentialities of the C2M model to the analysis and improvement of the communication, being this an innovator model that aims the improvement of the communication in the organizations, seeking to minimize the challenges of the impersonality, absence of effective communication, in addition to the physical, geographical and cultural distances. The C2M can be used as a polyvalent tool to support the communicative process of the organization.

In this question, thirty-six affirmed that the model is well organized and the number of levels is satisfactory. However, nine respondents pointed that the C2M model should have five maturity levels, in order to be in line with the CMMI. Still in their viewpoint, this change in the C2M would ease its acceptance by the organizations. Corroborating this idea, the Expert 1 affirms that “C2M would have a greater acceptance if adapted or adherent to the Carnegie-Mellon’s CMMI with 5 levels”. The Expert 4, supporting the matter in vogue, said that “is necessary to make a parallel of the C2M with the CMMI to a company, from the CMMI implementation, know where it can treat elements of the C2M, to a greater diffusion of the model.”

In minor instance, we observed some disagreeing positions in relation to its potentialities. We had three experts that disagreed with the level 1 of the C2M. In their viewpoint, if the level does not evolve, there is no reason to present it in the model. The Expert 10 affirms that “an interesting approach is the used by the MPS.BR, because since the first level the organization is already evolving”. Supporting this affirmative, the Expert 5 says that “there is a tendency of the researchers and universities in following the already existent models. However, models like the CMMI can be not the best alternative. I think that a model needs to be lean to be used by the companies. It is not worth to maintain a level that does not evolve.”

The other experts gave suggestions about the improvement of the nomenclature of the names of every level, as well as analyzed possible groupings in some levels.

In the other question, we asked if the C2M maturity levels represent a natural path for evolution (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - C2m Model as a natural path for evolution. Source: the author

In front of the exposed in the Figure 55 above, we can note that the level 1 obtained a positive acceptance. That is, forty-five experts (82%) answered “Yes”. In the level 2, thirty-nine experts (71%) answered “Yes”. In the level 3, forty-three experts (78%) answered “Yes”. And, at last, in the level 4, forty-eight (87%) answered “Yes”.

The expert 22 says that “the approach followed by the C2M is the better alternative, since it is an approach that initially considers that a company does not have maturity and evolve with things that make sense to the organization”. Still in this sense, the Expert 13 says that “It is important the initiative of conceiving a communication model, because, although being new, the C2M is well organized, showing an interesting naturality”. Finishing, the Expert 30 says that “the model have a natural and gradual path to the improvement of the communicative process of every company, being it small, medium or large.”

In the level 2, we obtained some negative answers. Sixteen experts (29%) answered “No” and next, in the level three, twelve experts (22%) answered “No”. Both levels concentrated a reater number of negative answers when comparing to the levels 1 and 4. The Expert 44 says that “It is normal the existence of rejections and acceptances when conceiving a new process, methodology or model. Over time, the model starts to maturate, reduce gaps and obtain greater acceptance of the target public.” At last, the Expert 12 says that “the C2M model still is in a little gradual sequence to micro and small companies. However, as a first version, it already has very much to contribute”

3.2 C2M MATURITY FACTORS AND PRACTICES

Level 1 should contain one or more maturity factors associated the it (Figure 5).

Figure 5 – Level 1. the author

According to the Figure 56, we can note that most of the experts wish that the level 1 stay without maturity factors. However, the other experts opted to insert some factor by the following reasons: The Expert 9 said that “is necessary to

include in this level elements/characteristics of the communication, even informal, inside the software processes implemented by the companies or professionals.” Next, the Expert 33 evidences that is necessary to have “tools to support the communication and the IT Infrastructure. These factors are implemented by organizations to establish the basic level, that is, level 1 of communication between teams and offshore insourcing services.” On his turn, the Expert 55 affirms that “It is worth the insertion of at least on factor in the level 1 about a “minimum” that a company treats in the area of communication in software processes.”

In sequence, we asked if the maturity factors in the Levels 2,3 and 4 are organized in the C2M model correctly (Figure 6).

Figure 6 - maturity factors in the Levels 2,3 and 4. Source: the author

The idea was to identify gaps, mistakes and/or possibility for improvement. In light of the scenario exposed by the Figure 57, many experts gave their opinion aiming to improve the C2M. The expert 1 said that “the configuration management would be in the level two, to stay in line with other models.” Next, the Expert 21, supporting the previous affirmation, says that “the configuration management is very important in DSD projects, and, for this reason, it must be in the level 2. Another factor that should be in the level two is measurement and analysis, because there is a famous sentence that says: If you cannot measure, you cannot manage.

The Expert 49 describes that “some practices are linked to the more generic context, as in other models, and are not specific only of communication in DSD. In my opinion, the model should focus only in what regards to the communication itself.”

The Expert 50 says that “the communication management is a very important item and it should be in the level 2. In its turn, the risk management could be in the level 3 as part of a more mature process.

The expert 52 explains that “there should be a maturity factor most associated to the called soft skills or personal attributes and competences. Please understand that the factor I am referring is different of the factor “Managing the Stakeholders.”

Next, the Figure 7 presents us the adherence of the objectives of each factor in the opinion of the experts.

Figure 7 – About the objectives of the C2M maturity factors. Source: the author

In this question, thirty-eight experts had their opinions diversified and consensual about the description of the factors, except by twelve opinions of experts who suggested simple modifications, and five experts who suggested the complete rewrite of the objectives of some maturity factors. The dominant though that inconsciously filiates to the thought of these seventeen experts who suggested the modification or rewriting of the objectives of the maturity factors links the maturity model for the communication in DSD, in such way that the set

of ideas and arguments does not contemplate a macro vision of its use in the organizations.

However, the dominant perspective in the talks refers to the contributions the C2M can provide to the community in the sense of the professionals using the model in every project and in every dispersion level.

Between the divergent discourses, the objectives of the factors which are evolved in the C2M model were the most criticized and subject to changes and rewritings.

In this sense, the Expert 28 says that “the objectives of the factors must be refined, specifically for those which are evolved to the next levels.” The expert 29 affirms that “the factors must be better described to understand the differences between the levels. For example: Elicitation and Specification of the requirements.”

Next, in the following question, we asked if the practices of the levels two, three and four are clearly and effectively described (Figure 8).

Figure 8 – About the descriptions of the practices of the levels 2, 3 and 4 of C2M. Source: the author

We are in front of antagonistic opinions; however, the research had presented an interesting adherence of the proposal of the maturity model with the evaluation of the experts. Consequently, the opinions reveal an “almost” discursive standardization (conceptual alignment) between the experts, whose are based

and related under distinct aspects and perspectives in the professional scope, being it in the software industry or academy.

The Expert 3 affirms that “the factor manage the organizational culture would be established with practices that help to know and evolve the organizational culture from the level and to the level 4. It would be interesting to clarify or cite examples of how to implement a certain practice”. The Expert 38 says that “the practices are very relevant, but a calibration, redistribution and redefinition in some points will strengthen the model very much.” At last, the Expert 5 describes that “Is not enough to have the best description of the practice, but is needed that it makes sense in the organization. As I understand, the maturity model does not say how to do, it says what to do.”

3.3 C2M MODEL IN GENERAL

Although the model is an initiative from the academy, the specialists affirmed that the proposal is highly relevant to the industry, being it of software or not. So, this evaluation corroborates what was said by the specialists in the focus group in the Section 4.4.

From the 55 interviewed experts, ten said that the model is simple to implement. Twenty-seven affirmed that the implementation of the C2M model is regular and at last eighteen that the implementation of the model is moderately complex (Figure 9).

Figure 9 – Complexity level of the C2M implementation. Source: the author

Once most of the experts (49%) affirmed that the implementation of the C2M model is regular, this leads us to believe that there is an influence of this over the adoption or not of this model in a DSD project (Figure 10).

Figure 10 - Experts whose would adopt the C2M in DSD projects. Source: the author

The Table 53a and 53b shows the influence of the time of experience in some questions of the interview script.

On the table 1 can be verified the significant association ($p < 0,05$) between the time of experience and the questions described in the Table. To the variables with significant association that are pointed the greater perceptual differences.

Table 1a – Relationship influences the experience in DSD with some answers of Experts.

Variable	Experience time in DSD (years)				Total group		p-value
	3 to 4		5 or more		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
TOTAL	30	100,0	25	100,0	55	100,0	

In your opinion, the maturity factors contained in the levels 2, 3 or 4 of the C2M Model are adequately distributed for the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

Yes, no changes are required.	12	40,0	10	40,0	22	40,0	$p^{(1)} = 0,493^*$
No, one or more maturity factors must be included.	3	10,0	5	20,0	8	14,5	

No, one or more maturity factors must be excluded.	2	6,7	4	16,0	6	10,9
No, one or more maturity factors must be grouped.	2	6,7	1	4,0	3	5,5
No, one or more maturity factors must be updated.	11	36,7	5	20,0	16	29,1

In your opinion, the objectives of the maturity factors which compose the levels 2, 3 and 4 of the C2M model are adequately described?

Yes, the factors are coherently described.	18	60,0	17	68,0	35	63,6	p ⁽¹⁾ = 0,055
Yes, partially clear and effective	1	3,3	4	16,0	5	9,1	
No, the description of one or more factors need of few adjusts.	-	-	1	4,0	1	1,8	
No, the description of one or more factors must be totally rewritten.	-	-	-	-	-	-	
No, the description of one or more factors must be partially rewritten.	11	36,7	3	12,0	14	25,5	

(*): Significant association at the level of 5,0%.

(1): Through the exact Fischer test.

Table 2b – Relationship influences the experience in DSD with some answers of Experts.

Variable	Experience time in DSD (years)				Total group		p-value
	3 to 4		5 or more		n	%	
	n	%	n	%			
TOTAL	30	100,0	25	100,0	55	100,0	

In your opinion, The practices of the factors of the level 2 – partially managed are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

Yes, the practices are coherently described.	15	50,0	13	52,0	28	50,9	p ⁽¹⁾ = 0,653
Yes, partially clear and effective	4	13,3	1	4,0	5	9,1	
No, the description of one or more factors need of few adjusts.	-	-	1	4,0	1	1,8	
No, the description of one or more factors must be totally rewritten.	2	6,7	1	4,0	3	5,5	
No, the description of one or more factors must be partially rewritten.	9	30,0	9	36,6	18	32,7	

In your opinion, The practices of the factors of the level 3 - managed are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

Yes, the practices are coherently described.	19	63,3	13	52,0	32	58,2	p ⁽¹⁾ = 0,204
Yes, partially clear and effective	3	10,0	5	20,0	8	14,5	
No, the description of one or more practices need of few adjusts.	-	-	3	12,0	3	5,5	
No, the description of one or more practices must be totally rewritten.	1	3,3	-	-	1	1,8	
No, the description of one or more practices must be partially rewritten.	7	23,3	4	16,6	11	20,0	

In your opinion, The practices of the factors of the level 4 - reflexive are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

Yes, the practices are coherently described.	18	60,0	18	72,0	36	65,5	p ⁽¹⁾ = 0,099
Yes, partially clear and effective	3	10,0	5	20,0	8	14,5	
No, the description of one or more practices need of few adjusts.	-	-	-	-	-	-	
No, the description of one or more practices must be totally rewritten.	1	3,3	1	4,0	2	3,6	
No, the description of one or more practices must be partially rewritten.	8	26,7	1	4,0	9	16,4	

In the Table 3, is presented the correlation between the decisions of every type of experience (Professional of the software industry, researcher and both) in the decisions of the experts. The focus of this table is to verify if there is a significant association ($p < 0,05$) between the type of experience and the questions described in the Table. To the variables with significant associations that are pointed the highest perceptual differences.

Table 3 – Relationship influences the type of experience in DSD with some answers of Experts.

Variable	Type of experience								p-Value
	Software industry		Research		Software industry and Research		Total Group		
	N	%	n	%	n	%	n	%	
TOTAL	14	100,0	19	100,0	22	100,0	55	100,0	

In your opinion, the maturity factors contained in the levels 2, 3 or 4 of the C2M Model are adequately distributed for the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

Yes, no changes are required.	5	35,7	13	68,4	4	18,2	22	40,0	$p^{(1)} = 0,012^*$
No, one or more maturity factors must be included.	5	35,7	-	-	3	13,6	8	14,5	
No, one or more maturity factors must be excluded.	1	7,1	1	5,3	4	18,2	6	10,9	
No, one or more maturity factors must be grouped.	-	-	1	5,3	2	9,1	3	5,5	
No, one or more maturity factors must be updated.	3	21,4	4	21,1	9	40,9	16	29,1	

In your opinion, the objectives of the maturity factors which compose the levels 2, 3 and 4 of the C2M model are adequately described?

Yes, the factors are coherently described.	10	71,4	14	73,7	11	35	35	63,6	$p^{(1)} = 0,010^*$
No, one or more maturity factors must be excluded.	3	21,4	-	-	2	9,1	5	9,1	
No, one or more maturity factors must be moved.	1	7,1	-	-	-	-	1	1,8	
No, one or more maturity factors must be grouped.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
No, one or more maturity factors must be updated.	-	-	5	26,3	9	40,9	14	25,5	

In your opinion, The practices of the factors of the level 2 – partially managed are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

Yes, the practices are coherently described.	8	57,1	13	68,4	7	31,8	28	50,9	$p^{(1)} = 0,028^*$
Yes, partially clear and effective	3	21,4	1	5,3	1	4,5	5	9,1	
No, the description of one or more practices need of few adjusts.	1	7,1	-	-	-	-	1	1,8	
No, the description of one or more practices must be totally rewritten.	-	-	1	5,3	2	9,1	3	5,5	
No, the description of one or more practices must be partially rewritten.	2	14,3	4	21,1	12	54,5	18	32,7	

In your opinion, The practices of the factors of the level 3 - managed are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

Yes, the practices are coherently described.	12	85,7	13	68,4	7	31,8	32	58,2	$p^{(1)} = 0,022^*$
Yes, partially clear and effective	1	7,1	3	15,8	4	18,2	8	14,5	
No, the description of one or more practices need of few adjusts.	1	7,1	-	-	2	9,1	3	5,5	
No, the description of one or more practices must be totally rewritten.	-	-	-	-	1	4,5	1	1,8	
No, the description of one or more practices must be partially rewritten.	-	-	3	15,8	8	36,4	11	20,0	

In your opinion, The practices of the factors of the level 4 - reflexive are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

Yes, the practices are coherently described.	10	71,4	12	63,2	14	63,6	36	65,5	$p^{(1)} = 0,864$
Yes, partially clear and effective	2	14,3	3	15,8	3	13,6	8	14,5	

No, the description of one or more practices need of few adjusts.	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
No, the description of one or more practices must be totally rewritten.	1	7,1	1	5,3	-	-	2	3,6
No, the description of one or more practices must be partially rewritten.	1	7,1	3	15,8	5	22,7	9	16,4

3.4 BENEFITS OF C2M ACCORDING THE EXPERTS

After the interviews, the experts were inquired about what benefits the C2M brings to the DSD projects.

Expert 1 said that the main benefit is “the adoption of well-defined practices for the communication. A good communication makes the project have a more smooth execution.” Next, Expert 2 affirms that “the model can organize and structure projects with distributed teams to better use the communicational synergy between teams, raising the productivity, reducing costs and maintaining the quality of the final product.

On his turn, expert 3 said that the greater benefit is “the communication maturity itself in a DSD project or in a company itself, where all the projects would start to be used inside that level, what highly eases all the process of software development to distributed teams”. Strengthening this idea, the Expert 4 describes that “the C2M model presents guidelines which will allow a more planned and structured communication, executing then the tasks more effectively.

Expert 5 said that “the greater benefit is to make the management reflect about the importance of several aspects (factors and practices) that often are neglected.”

Among the main benefits cited by the Experts, we point:

- The importance of the communication management;
- A systematic way to plan and better understand the problem of the communication in projects and in the organization;
- Good communication practices;
- Effective communication;
- More transparency, better results, decrease of the conflicts, understanding and follow up of the projects;

- Establish the effective management of the communication between teams;
- Minimize the impact of the lack of interpersonal contact.

4 CONSIDERATIONS

This report presented the definition, planning, operation, analysis and interpretation of the study based on expert opinion that evaluated the feasibility, completeness and adequacy of the C2M maturity model.

For 65% (36) of the experts said it would adopt the model and 33% (18) of the experts said they possibly adopt. Only 2% (1) expert said it would not adopt. This result motivates us to invest heavily in continuous improvement of C2M so that it can assist organizations in organizational processes effectively.

Even with the reduced number of experts (55), the analysis has shown that the C2M can be feasible.

The study also identified some directions for improvements that will be analyzed and subsequently generated a new version of the proposed model. This activity is already planned in our future work.